

Global Warming over the Ocean 1850-1880

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Abstract

The available dataset of global warming over the ocean is for the 1880-2021 period. This publication estimates the global warming over the ocean for 1850-1880, using existing data of global warming over land and global warming over land+ocean.

Glossary

AL	global area of land, %
AO	global area of the ocean, %
BL	baseline of surface temperature change (GW) 1850-1900
GW	Global Warming, global surface temperature above the 1850-1900 baseline, land+ocean, °C
GWL	global surface temperature over land only, above the 1850-1900 baseline, °C
GWO	global surface temperature over the ocean only, above the 1850-1900 baseline, °C

Introduction

The dataset for global warming over the ocean is for the period 1880-2021 [1] [2] [3].

The current work attempts to estimate global warming over the ocean for the period 1850-1880 based on formulas and calculations published in the publication [7].

Global Warming Baseline

All global warming data in this publication are above the 1850-1900 baseline, °C.

Global Warming Dataset

The dataset of global surface temperature changes for land and the ocean (GW) converted to the 1850-1900 baseline is publicly available on [1]. It is based on NASA [2] [3], NOAA [4], and Berkley Earth [5] [6].

The dataset for global warming over land is for 1750-2021 and over the ocean 1880-2021.

Table 1 - [Available global warming data \[1\]](#)

		from	to
Land only	GWL	1750	2021
Ocean only	GWO	1880	2021
Land+Ocean	GW	1850	2021

Formula for Calculation of Global Warming over the Ocean

Publication [7] includes a formula for determination of the global warming over land and over the ocean based on data over land and data over the ocean.

Formula 1 - Calculation of GW using GWL and GWO according to land and ocean area [7]

$$\mathbf{GW = GWL * AL + GWO * AO}$$

GW Global Warming, global surface temperature above the 1850-1900 baseline, land+ocean, °C

GWL global surface temperature over the land only above the 1850-1900 baseline, °C

GWO global surface temperature over the ocean only, above the 1850-1900 baseline, °C

AL global area of land, %

AO global area of the ocean, %

AL and AO are determined in the publication [7] as follows:

Based on the Global Warming data, the average land area (AL) in the period 1990-2021 was 31.18% of the total area of the Earth, and the ocean area (AO) was 68.82%.

Table 2 - Land area and ocean area [7]

Global Land Area	AL	31.18%
Global Ocean Area	AO	68.82%

The dataset for global warming over the ocean is for the period 1880-2021 [1] [2] [3].

The above formula allows calculations of Global Warming over the ocean (GWO) for the missing years in the NASA dataset [2] [3].

Formula 2 - Determination of GWO, °C

$$\mathbf{GWO = (GW - GWL*AL) / AO}$$

Global Warming over the Ocean in 1850-1880Table 3 - Global warming over the ocean (GWO) in 1850-1880, °C above the 1850-1900 baseline

	GW [1]	GWL [1]	GWO
1850	-0.133	-0.339	-0.040
1851	-0.018	-0.056	-0.001
1852	0.009	-0.163	0.087
1853	0.011	-0.169	0.093
1854	0.013	0.022	0.009
1855	0.023	-0.047	0.054
1856	-0.092	-0.151	-0.065
1857	-0.233	-0.401	-0.157
1858	-0.026	0.000	-0.038
1859	0.087	0.183	0.043
1860	-0.066	-0.218	0.003
1861	-0.146	-0.273	-0.088
1862	-0.260	-0.646	-0.085
1863	-0.039	-0.004	-0.055
1864	-0.049	-0.174	0.008
1865	0.054	0.042	0.060
1866	0.106	0.161	0.081
1867	0.149	0.311	0.076
1868	0.104	0.038	0.134
1869	0.097	0.300	0.005
1870	0.022	-0.013	0.038
1871	-0.022	-0.127	0.026
1872	0.008	-0.047	0.033
1873	0.045	0.122	0.010
1874	-0.002	0.251	-0.117
1875	-0.039	-0.267	0.064
1876	-0.041	-0.040	-0.041
1877	0.341	0.363	0.331
1878	0.428	0.730	0.291
1879	0.081	0.037	0.101
1880	0.109	-0.101	0.204

Chart 1 - Global warming over land and over the ocean, °C above the 1850-1900 baseline

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